

NEMECYS

NEW MEDICAL CYBERSECURITY AND DESIGN SOLUTIONS

Secure Software Development Pipelines

SSDP

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Disclaimer

The NEMECYS project is co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101094323, by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee grant numbers 10065802, 10050933 and 10061304, and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

The information and views set out in this publication are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, HADEA, UKRI or SERI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

1 Introduction

Welcome to this guide on setting up Secure Software Development Pipelines (SSDP UI) using Jenkins. This document will walk you through the entire process, from installation to create a pipeline to managing secure deployments.

2 Requirements

Requirements for first pilots are not needed as it will be deployed on ICE Servers to demonstrate SSDP. For Second Pilot these are the minimal requirements:

Test Production (KubeAdm).

- Multiple VMs required for High availability.

Test Profile(K3s):

- 1 VM
 - o Mem (Min 8GB)
 - o CPU (4CPUs)
 - o HD 50Gb
- VMs Ubuntu 18+ (Masters, Slaves, Environments)
 - o Mem (Min 8GB)
 - o CPU (4CPUs)
 - o HD 50Gb
- Installation script:
 - o Docker
 - o Kubernetes 1.20 +
 - o SSDP (Jenkins)
 - o SSDP Plugins and Shared Libraries (ICE Repository)
 - o Rancher
 - o Helm
 - Helm chart app (for pilot 2 as it will require Kubernetes and Helm to be installed)
 - Go (for ICE Helm Plugin)

External Services :

- Gitlab
 - o Application
 - o Helm charts.
 - o Templates.

3 Prerequisites

Before starting the deployment, ensure the following software is installed and configured:

Component	Version	Notes
IceKube	v3.0	Refer to official IceKube Repository for installation
Helm	v3.17.2	
Docker Engine	24.0.2	
k3s	v1.30.6+k3s1	
SonarQube	8.9.1.44547	
Jenkins Helm Chart	5.4.3	
JDK	11.0.19	
Jenkins Controller Image	2.462.1-jdk17	
Redis	8.2.2	
Mongo	8.0.15	

Table 1 Prerequisites

Reference: IceKube Repository (<https://git.icelab.cloud/nemecys/connector>)

Token: glpat-7SYahvMnf18U1WJD5Bip

```
git clone https://connector:glpat-7SYahvMnf18U1WJD5Bip@git.icelab.cloud/nemecys/connector.git
```


Video: <https://youtu.be/v4HOvzK2GQU>

4 DEPLOY

This section provides step-by-step instructions to deploy Jenkins and the SSDP UI.

4.1 Step 1: Clone the Repository

Clone the Jenkins repository using the following command:

```
git clone https://git.icelab.cloud/nemecys/jenkins.git
```


Video: <https://youtu.be/DhAaNI4KoyY>

4.2 Step 2: Modify Configuration

Open the `values.yaml` file located at `jenkins/install/ssdp-ui/` in a text editor and modify the necessary values. See

1. 02 - SSDP PLATFORM DEPLOYMENT CONFIGURATION GUIDE (Values.yaml)

2. 06 - HOW TO CREATE OAUTH APPLICATION

4.3 Step 3: Copy Installation Directory to VM

Copy the **install** directory from the cloned repository to your VM.

 Video: <https://youtu.be/RvalNNRxfnU>

4.4 Step 4: Run the Installation Script

Navigate to the directory on your VM and execute the installation script:

```
cd install
sudo bash install_new.sh IP_ADDRES
```

Example Execution

```
cd install
sudo bash install_new.sh 192.168.20.225
```

 Video: <https://youtu.be/p4xKWxxfRrM>

4.5 Step 5: Verify the Installation

To verify that the installation was successful, run the following command:

```
kubectl get all,sa,pvc -n ssdp
```

 Video: <https://youtu.be/WejxqJWE67w>

This should return a list of deployed resources similar to the following output:

```
vagrant@ubuntu:~$ kubectl get all,sa,pvc -n ssdp
NAME                                READY   STATUS    RESTARTS   AGE
pod/report-nodejs-deployment-5c967764f6-kjgqh  1/1     Running   0           42h
pod/report-vuejs-deployment-6749bb6995-mfnr7  1/1     Running   0           42h
pod/ssdp-jenkins-0                          2/2     Running   1 (42h ago)  42h

NAME                                TYPE                                CLUSTER-IP    EXTERNAL-IP    PORT(S)          AGE
service/report-nodejs-service        NodePort        10.43.164.6   <none>         31000:31000/TCP  42h
service/report-vuejs-service         NodePort        10.43.221.158 <none>         80:31500/TCP    42h
service/ssdp-jenkins                 NodePort        10.43.233.1   <none>         8080:32000/TCP  42h
service/ssdp-jenkins-agent           ClusterIP       10.43.201.219 <none>         50000/TCP       42h

NAME                                READY   UP-TO-DATE   AVAILABLE   AGE
deployment.apps/report-nodejs-deployment  1/1     1             1           42h
deployment.apps/report-vuejs-deployment   1/1     1             1           42h

NAME                                DESIRED   CURRENT   READY   AGE
replicaset.apps/report-nodejs-deployment-5c967764f6  1         1         1       42h
replicaset.apps/report-vuejs-deployment-6749bb6995  1         1         1       42h

NAME                                READY   AGE
statefulset.apps/ssdp-jenkins        1/1     42h

NAME                                SECRETS   AGE
serviceaccount/default               0         42h
serviceaccount/ssdp-jenkins          0         42h

NAME                                STATUS    VOLUME    CAPACITY   ACCESS MODES   STORAGECLASS   AGE
persistentvolumeclaim/jenkins-pv-cache-claim  Bound    jenkins-cache-pv-volume  5Gi          RW0            jenkins-cache-storage  42h
persistentvolumeclaim/jenkins-pv-claim        Bound    jenkins-home-pv-volume   5Gi          RW0            jenkins-storage       42h
persistentvolumeclaim/jenkins-pv-report-claim Bound    jenkins-report-pv-volume  5Gi          RW0            jenkins-report-storage 42h
```

Figure 1 Deployed resources

SSDP (Jenkins) - http://<IP>:32000

Figure 2 SSDP (Jenkins)

GUI -http://<IP>:31500

Figure 3 Sign In

5 SSDP PLATFORM DEPLOYMENT CONFIGURATION GUIDE (Values.yaml)

This section describes the configuration used to deploy the **SSDP Platform** via Helm.

The platform is composed of the following core components:

- **Node.js Backend** - Handles APIs, authentication, and integrations
- **Vue.js Frontend** - Web UI for managing pipelines and reports

- **Redis** - In-memory cache and session store
- **MongoDB** - Persistent database for configurations and reports

5.1 Node.js Backend Configuration values

The Node.js service powers the backend APIs, manages authentication, integrations with Jenkins, SonarQube, and Git providers, and handles reporting logic.

Parameter	Description	Example / Default
replicaCount	Number of backend pods	1
image.repository	Docker image repository	jnithushan/ssdp-ui-backend
image.tag	Image version tag	1.1.3
imagePullPolicy	Pull policy for image	Always
containerPort	Exposed backend container port	31000
pvcName	PVC name for Jenkins report data storage	jenkins-pv-report-claim
app.name	Application name	nodejs-app

Table 2 Node.js Backend Configuration Values

5.1.1 Configuration Map

Defines environment-specific and integration-related configurations for the backend.

Parameter	Description	Example
frontendUrl	URL of the Vue.js frontend	http://192.168.20.225:31500
sonarqubeUrl	SonarQube server URL	http://192.168.20.225:30012
appBaseUrl	Backend base URL	http://192.168.20.225:31000
jenkinsUrl	Jenkins server URL	http://192.168.20.225:32000
accessTokenExpiryInMinutes	JWT access token lifetime (in minutes)	"2"
refreshTokenExpiryInDays	JWT refresh token lifetime (in days)	"5"
nodeEnv	Node environment (e.g., development/production)	"development"
cookieMaxAge	Cookie validity duration (in milliseconds)	"43200000"
gitlabClientId	GitLab OAuth Client ID	b641df3e...caf5dde
githubClientId	GitHub OAuth Client ID	Ov23likRC3..upxuGm
ATCFileUploadUrl	ATC file upload API endpoint	https://nemecys-be.lab.atc.gr/tests

ATCFileUploadAuthUrl	ATC authentication API endpoint	https://nemecys-be.lab.atc.gr/auth/login
----------------------	---------------------------------	--

5.1.2 Secret Configuration

Sensitive credentials used for authentication, encryption, and third-party API access.

Secret Key	Description
accessTokenSecret	Secret for JWT access tokens
refreshTokenSecret	Secret for JWT refresh tokens
sessionSecret	Secret used for encrypting session data
gitlabClientSecret	GitLab OAuth client secret (base64 encoded)
githubClientSecret	GitHub OAuth client secret (base64 encoded)
ATCFileUploadusername	ATC API username (base64 encoded)
ATCFileUploadPassword	ATC API password (base64 encoded)

5.1.3 Service Configuration

Parameter	Description	Value
type	Kubernetes service type	NodePort
port	Internal service port	31000
nodePort	External node port	31000

5.1.4 Resource Allocation

Type	CPU	Memory
Requests	500m	1Gi
Limits	1000m	3Gi

5.2 Vue.js Frontend Configuration values

The Vue.js service provides the web-based SSDP interface for managing pipelines, credentials, and reports.

Parameter	Description	Example / Default
image.repository	Frontend Docker image	jnithushan/ssdp-ui-frontend
image.tag	Image version	1.1.3
imagePullPolicy	Image pull policy	Always
containerPort	Container port exposed by frontend	31500

Table 3 Vue.js Frontend Configuration Values

5.2.1 Service Configuration

Parameter	Description	Value
port	Internal service port	80

targetPort	Container target port	80
nodePort	External NodePort for UI	31500

5.2.2 Resource Allocation

Type	CPU	Memory
Requests	500m	512Mi
Limits	1000m	2Gi

5.2.3 Redis Cache Configuration Values

The Redis instance is used for caching and managing session data, improving backend performance.

Parameter	Description	Value
image	Redis image and version	redis:8.2.2
host	Redis host IP	192.168.20.225

Table 4 Redis Cache Configuration Values

5.2.4 Service Configuration

Parameter	Description	Value
port	Internal port	6379
targetPort	Target container port	6379
nodePort	External NodePort (optional)	32023

5.2.5 Resource Allocation

Type	CPU	Memory
Requests	250m	1Gi
Limits	500m	2Gi

5.3 MongoDB Database Configuration Values

The MongoDB instance stores persistent application data, including pipeline configurations, user settings, and reports.

Parameter	Description	Value
image	MongoDB image and version	mongo:8.0.15
host	MongoDB host IP	192.168.20.225
initdb.database	Default database name	ssdp_db

Table 5 MongoDB Database Configuration Values

5.3.1 Authentication

Key	Description	Encoded Value
rootUserName	Base64-encoded MongoDB root username	c3NkcHJvb3R1c2Vy
rootPassword	Base64-encoded MongoDB root password	c3NkcG1vbmdvMWFkbWl u

5.3.2 Service Configuration

Parameter	Description	Value
port	Internal service port	27017
targetPort	Container target port	27017
nodePort	External NodePort (optional)	32012

5.3.3 Resource Allocation

Type	CPU	Memory
Requests	500m	1Gi
Limits	1000m	3Gi

5.4 Summary of Ports

Component	Purpose	NodePort
Backend	API & Integrations	31000
Frontend	Web UI	31500
Redis	Cache	32023
MongoDB	Database	32012

Table 6 Summary of Ports

6 SETTING UP SSDP

This document provides step-by-step instructions to set up SSDP, including configuring the pipeline library and adding nodes.

 Video: <https://youtu.be/3WfKB6888QU>

6.1 Configuring the Pipeline Library

To configure the pipeline library, follow these steps:

1. Navigate to **Dashboard > Manage SSDP > System > Global Trusted Pipeline Libraries**.
2. Click **Add Library** and enter the following details:
 - **Name:** `shared-library`
 - **Default Version:** `report-v1.0.4`
 - **Retrieval Method:** `Modern SCM`
 - **Project Repository:** `https://git.icelab.cloud/nemecys/ssdp/jenkins-libraries.git`
3. Configure **Credentials**:
 - **Kind:** `Username with Password`
 - **Scope:** `Global`
 - **Username:** `[user_name]`
 - **Token:** `[token]`
 - **ID:** `PIPELINE-LIBRARY-TOKEN` ● **Description:**
`PIPELINE LIBRARY TOKEN`
4. Click **Save** to apply the changes.

6.2 Adding Nodes

To add nodes to SSDP, follow these steps:

 Video: <https://youtu.be/MuVo3qBXEaA>

1. Navigate to **Dashboard > Manage SSDP > Nodes**.

- Status
- Delete Agent
- Configure
- Build History
- Load Statistics
- Script Console
- Log
- System Information
- Disconnect
- Open Blue Ocean

Build Executor Status

- 1 Idle
- 2 Idle

Name ?

ubuntu

Description ?

Plain text [Preview](#)

Number of executors ?

2

Remote root directory ?

/home/vagrant/agent

Labels ?

linux docker ubuntu

Usage ?

Use this node as much as possible

Launch method ?

Launch agents via SSH

Host ?

ubuntu

Credentials ?

vagrant

+ Add

Host Key Verification Strategy ?

Non verifying Verification Strategy

Advanced

Edited

Availability ?

Keep this agent online as much as possible

Save

Figure 4 Jenkins Nodes

Jenkins Credentials Provider: Jenkins

Kind

Username with password

Scope ?

Global (Jenkins, nodes, items, all child items, etc)

Username ?

vagrant

Treat username as secret ?

Password ?

.....

ID ?

vagrant

Description ?

vagrant

Cancel Add

Figure 5 Jenkins Credentials

6.3 Setting Up Cluster Credentials

Follow the steps below to configure your Kubernetes cluster credentials for SSDP:

1. Obtain the kubeconfig file of your Kubernetes cluster.

On your cluster server, run the following command and save the output to a file:

```
cat ~/.kube/config
```

2. Add the kubeconfig file as a credential in SSDP:

- Navigate to: Dashboard > Manage SSDP > Credentials > System > Global Credentials > Add Credentials
- Configure the fields as follows:
 - Kind: Secret file
 - Scope: Global
 - File: [Upload the kubeconfig file obtained in the previous step]
 - ID: [Specify the ID that corresponds to the global environment variable used in your project.]

For example (see the image below):

- `kubeconfig-home1` → used for `CI_CLUSTER`, `QA_CLUSTER`, and `SEC_CLUSTER`
- `kubeconfig-home2` → used for `PER_CLUSTER`

Figure 6 Kubernetes Kube config

- Description: [Provide a relevant description for the credential]

3. Repeat this process for each cluster ID used in your global environment variable setup:

`CI_CLUSTER`, `QA_CLUSTER`, `SEC_CLUSTER`, `PER_CLUSTER`, `STA_CLUSTER`, and `PRO_CLUSTER`.

6.4 SonarQube Configuration

Follow the steps below to configure the SonarQube server in SSDP.

6.4.1 Generate a SonarQube Token

1. Go to your SonarQube server interface.
2. Click on your profile icon (top-right corner) and select My Account.
3. Navigate to the Security tab.
4. Under Generate Tokens, enter a name for the token and click Generate.
5. Copy the generated token, it will be used in the SSDP configuration.

6.4.2 Add a New Credential for the SonarQube Token

1. Navigate to:

Dashboard > Manage SSDP > Credentials > System > Global credentials

2. Click Add Credentials.
3. Configure the following fields:
 - Kind: Secret text
 - Scope: Global

- Secret: [Enter the SonarQube token value]
- ID: SonarQube-token ○ Description: SonarQube-token

6.4.3 Configure the SonarQube Server

1. Navigate to: Dashboard > Manage SSDP > System
2. Scroll down to the **SonarQube Servers** section.
3. Configure the following fields:
 - Server URL: [Your sonarqube server URL (example http://192.168.50.235:30012)] ○
 - Server Authentication Token: SonarQube-token

Figure 7 SonarQube Configuration

PROJECT SETUP GUIDE

This section provides a step-by-step guide for setting up a project in SSDP using the user interface. It covers project configuration, environment variable setup, source code upload, Git repository configuration, and Jenkins pipeline creation. [📺 Video: https://youtu.be/duS0fx-gHck](https://youtu.be/duS0fx-gHck)

7.1 Step 1: Navigating to Project Configuration

Navigate to the Project Configuration section and select the global language. This selection helps preconfigure various settings to align with the chosen language. For this demonstration, C# is selected.

Figure 8 SSCP UI Select Programming Language

7.2 Step 2 : Configuring Environment Variables

Explore the user interface and familiarize yourself with its key sections:

- The first two sections are dedicated to configuring environment variables for your pipeline.
- Click the “Apply Default” button in the top-right corner to automatically populate the fields with default values.
- Expand each section carefully and update the values according to your project requirements.
- Retain the default values where they are applicable.

7.2.1 Pipeline Stage Configuration

This section allows enabling or disabling specific pipeline functionalities:

- Select which stages to execute in the development pipeline.
- Retain default settings if applicable.

7.3 Step 3: Uploading Source Code

 Video: https://youtu.be/sFqIVrJoM_Q

This section includes a file uploader for project source code:

- Upload a zipped archive containing your source code.
- Steps:
 1. Select relevant files.
 2. Compress them into a zip archive.
 3. Upload using the interface.

Figure 9 Source Code Uploader

Figure 10 Source code compress ZIP

7.4 Step 4: Setting Up the Git Repository

Video: <https://youtu.be/Bf3XFM7Jf94>

- Configure the Git repository and Jenkins pipelines:
- Enter the repository URL (e.g., GitLab or GitHub).
- Choose from three options:
 - Create a repository
 - Push the configured project to the repository
 - Download the configured project for manual Git push
- Log into the Git account and proceed with repository creation.

Figure 11 Repository Configuration

7.4.1 Configuring Jenkins Pipelines

Set up Jenkins folder structure to organize pipelines:

- Enter the desired folder hierarchy using slash (/) as a separator.
- Example:
 - Log into Jenkins using username and password.
- Create the specified folder.

7.4.2 Configuring Jenkins Credentials

Configure Jenkins credentials to allow access to the Git repository:

- Create a credential entry with the same ID specified in the Project Configuration.

Figure 12 Configure Jenkins Credentials

7.4.3 Creating Pipelines

Create pipelines:

1. Main
2. Development
3. CI
4. QA
5. Security
6. Performance
7. Staging
8. Production

Check the respective boxes and click on Create button to generate the pipelines.

Figure 13 Creating Pipelines Environments

8 REPORT GUI

8.1 Running the Pipeline

8.1.1 From the SSDP (Jenkins) Tool

📺 Video: <https://youtu.be/tPLazyzuvQ>

- Navigate to the main pipeline.
- Click Build Now to initiate the pipeline execution.
- During the process, the main pipeline will trigger other pipelines sequentially.
- This process may take some time, and certain stages may require manual approval before proceeding.

8.1.2 From the SSDP User Interface

- Click View Existing and navigate through your project folders to locate your pipeline list.

Figure 14 SSDP User Interface View Existing

- Open the main-pipeline and click Trigger Main Pipeline to start the build execution.

- At certain stages, you might be prompted to provide approval.
 - In the SSDP UI, click Show Logs or Refresh Logs to view input requests.
 - When prompted, you can proceed with your decision to approve or reject.

- Alternatively, approvals can also be managed directly from the SSDP (Jenkins) tool.

8.2 Viewing Generated Reports

📺 Video: https://youtu.be/kE5spQ_-9VM

Once the pipeline build is complete:

1. Navigate to your pipeline, you'll see a list of recent builds.
2. Click on any build to open its details.

From there:

- You will find several plain report files available for download or review.
- To view a summarized graphical representation:
 1. Click on the summary report file.
 2. Select the link labeled "Access the summary report GUI here."

Access summary report GUI [here](#)

Build Summary Report

3. You will be redirected to the SSDP User Interface, where the summary report form is automatically populated with values corresponding to your project configuration.
4. You can either modify the values or click the Get Summary button to generate the graphical visualization of the report.

The 'Report Form' is a configuration interface for generating reports. It includes the following fields and options:

- Job Name:** SSDP-JAVA/01-development
- Build Number:** 16
- Language:** Java
- Source Directory Name:** source
- Report Directory:** reports
- Pipeline Report Directory:** dev
- Sonar Project:** java-app
- Sonar URL:** http://192.168.20.225:30012

Select Reports for DEV:

- DEV_SEL_DEPENDENCIES
- DEV_SEL_CODE_QUALITY
- DEV_SEL_LINTING
- DEV_SEL_UNITTEST
- DEV_SEL_MUTTEST
- DEV_SEL_BUILD_ARTIFACTS

Figure 15 Viewing Generated Reports

8.3 Upload JSON Reports to ATC

Video: https://youtu.be/te3_pgO761Y

- In the JSON tab section of the UI, all reports are displayed in JSON format simultaneously.
- Adjust the depth of each JSON report individually for a more detailed view.
- Options include:
 - Downloading reports as JSON files.
 - Opening reports in a JSON viewer for better readability.

At the bottom of the screen:

- Select and download specific JSON files.

- Upload files using the Upload button, with an option to provide a description before submission.

Figure 16 Upload JSON Reports to ATC

8.4 Downloading Graphical Reports as PDF

 Video: <https://youtu.be/HlInluTxUewQ>

In the PDF Tab section, users can download a graphical visualization of their reports as a PDF.

Steps:

1. Select Reports: Choose which reports you would like to include in the PDF.
2. Download PDF: Once you've selected the desired reports, click the Download button. This will generate and download the PDF with your selected reports.

Figure 17 Downloading Graphical Reports as PDF

9 HOW TO CREATE OAUTH APPLICATION

9.1 GitLab

This section provides step-by-step instructions on how to create an OAuth application in GitLab.

9.1.1 Prerequisites

- You must have admin or maintainer access to the GitLab instance.
- Ensure you are logged into GitLab.

9.1.2 Steps to Create an OAuth Application

9.1.2.1 Step 1: Navigate to OAuth Applications

1. Log in to your GitLab account.
2. Click on your profile icon (top-right corner) and select Edit profile.

3. In the left sidebar, click on Applications.

9.1.2.2 Step 2: Register a New Application 1.

1. Click on Add new application.

2. Fill in the following details:

- Name: Enter a name for your application (e.g., "My OAuth App").
- Redirect URI: Enter the URL where users should be redirected after authentication. •
 http://<your_ip>:31000/api/git/gitlab/callback • Scopes: Select the required scopes (e.g., api).

Figure 18 GITLAB OAUTH APPLICATION

9.1.2.3 Step 3: Save and Obtain Credentials

1. Click Save application.
2. Copy and securely store the Application ID and Secret Key. These credentials will be required for authentication.

9.2 GitHub

This section provides step-by-step instructions on how to create an OAuth application in GitHub.

9.2.1 Prerequisites

- You must have a GitHub account.
- Ensure you have admin access to the organization or repository (if applicable).

9.2.2 Steps to Create an OAuth Application

9.2.2.1 Step 1: Navigate to Developer Settings

1. Log in to your GitHub account.
2. Click on your profile icon (top-right corner) and select Settings.

3. Scroll down and click on Developer settings (bottom-left sidebar).

4. Click on OAuth Apps.
5. Click New OAuth App.

9.2.2.2 Step 2: Register a New Application

1. Fill in the following details:
 - Application name: Enter a name for your application (e.g., "My OAuth App").
 - Homepage URL: Enter the main URL of your application.

- Authorization callback URL: Enter the URL where users should be redirected after authentication.
2. Click Register application.

Client secret: You cannot delete the only client secret. Generate a new client secret first.

Application logo: Upload new logo. You can also drag and drop a picture from your computer.

Application name *: SSDP

Homepage URL *: http://192.168.20.225:31000

Application description: Application description is optional. This is displayed to all users of your application.

Authorization callback URL *: http://192.168.20.225:31000/api/git/github/callback

Enable Device Flow. Allow this OAuth App to authorize users via the Device Flow. Read the Device Flow documentation for more information.

Figure 19 GitHub OAUTH APPLICATION

9.2.2.3 Step 3: Obtain Credentials

1. After registration, you will receive a Client ID.
2. Click Generate a new client secret to obtain the Client Secret.
3. Copy and securely store both the Client ID and Client Secret.

9.3 Encoding the Secret Key to Base64

To encode the secret key to Base64 using Git Bash, run the following command:

```
echo -n "your_secret_key" | base64
```

This will output the Base64-encoded version of your secret key. Ensure that you use `-n` to prevent adding a newline character.

10UI SETTINGS

10.1 Credentials Settings.

Here, you can update your SSDP credentials.

A list of available credentials will be displayed, click on any credential to select it, provide the new token, and then click Update Credential to save the changes.

Figure 20 SSDP UI Credentials Settings.

10.2 SonarQube Settings

10.2.1 In the SonarQube Server UI

1. Go to your SonarQube server interface.
2. Click on your profile icon (top-right corner) and select My Account.
3. Navigate to the Security tab.
4. Under Generate Tokens, enter a name for the token and click Generate.
5. Copy the generated token

10.2.2 2.2 In the SSDP UI

1. Go to Settings.
2. Click on SonarQube.
3. Click the Add New button.
4. Provide the SonarQube Server URL and the token obtained in the previous step.
5. Click Add to save the configuration.

Figure 21SSDP SonarQube Settings

10.3 Git Provider Settings

Refer to Section How to Create an OAuth Application to obtain the Client ID and Client Secret.

1. In the SSDP UI settings page, click on Git in the sidebar.
2. Click Add New Provider.
3. Select your base provider - **GitLab** or **GitHub**.
4. Enter the following details:
 - Integration Name: Any preferred name for this integration.
 - Base URL: For example, **https://git.icelab.cloud**
 - Client ID and Client Secret: Use the values obtained from the previous step.
5. Click Save Settings to complete the configuration.

Figure 22 SSDP UI Git Provider Settings